

Field Work in Social Work Education: An Onerous but Intrinsic Component

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Abstract

Much water has flown under the bridge regarding field work component as a part of social work education. However, despite the deluge, questions prevail. Not of its requirement, but of the nature and formats of field work. This paper takes the Indian setting as the base for a major part of its arguments, supported by evidence that makes the case for field work by a range of scholars of social work. It describes the complex character of field work and rationalizes how and why it maybe an onerous task to even presume that we can have a uniform or unique way of doing field work. Societies are positioned differently at different times in different places. The consequent issues requiring social work interventions are therefore vastly distinct and unique, being governed by multiple factors ranging from polity and economy, to religion and ethnicity. Thus, trying to etch out unique and uniform ways of practicing field work may perhaps have to wait for a little longer.

Keywords: *Field work, practice, profession, reflexivity, social work, situational learning*

Introduction

The Social Work curriculum is incomplete without its other half, i.e., field work. Marion Bogo (2005) observes how it is referred by various nomenclatures across the world. They range from field education, field instruction, field practicum, student supervision, practice learning etc. It is a very significant and essential component of social work education programs. Students gain first hand exposure for practice in government as well as non-government settings via educational programs. The aim of this component is onerous and cannot be taken lightly. Its extreme significance had been advocated by Mary Richmond (1917) in the early days of social work, when there were raging debates about formulating the social work curriculum and incorporating it as a university program (Austin, 1983). The rich field experience was what set social work apart.

Katherine A. Kendall (1959) points out the irrevocable and age-old tussle between practitioners and theorists amongst all professions. She notes that when practicum is a component of any learning program, the costs are high.

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Such is the fate of social work that it is ill placed to bolster itself to counter the intimidating forces of the other professions such as medicine or law, as questions about its professional status still abound. David Austin (1983) had rightfully rued that trying to measure up to the Flexner criteria also has added to its hassles of acquiring a professional status. Kendall (1959) additionally notes that much research has also not been done on the costs involved in field work and pushes for it. It would in fact open up a wide spectrum of information and justification as to why field work continues to be an overwhelming essence in social work education.

Reflexivity in Social Work

Field work seeks to enhance skill-based training and understanding of social work practice. The towering notion of field-based education in social work is to enmesh theory and practice and look at it as an integrated whole (Richmond, 1917). It seeks to provide students the scope to thus apply their classroom learnings in the field and vice versa. Reflexivity is thus embedded in the social work curriculum. Heather D’Cruz, Philip Gillingham, & Sebastian Melendez (2005) however caution us that confusion over reflexivity, critical reflection, and reflectivity must be avoided. They explain reflexivity in three variations. The first looks at reflexivity as an individual’s response and situational decision making. The second variant talks about the individual’s ability to process information and involves being self-critical and question the process of knowledge creation. Thirdly, it deals with the role of emotions in social work practice. They exemplify that power and knowledge are intricately interwoven and hence have a crucial role in influencing emancipatory practices in social work. They attribute such influence to social researchers Humphries and Truman (1994) and feminist sociologists, Stanley and Wise (1993).

Michael Sheppard (1998) additionally explains how reflexivity must engage the social worker in thinking, assessing, responding and acting; and must also participate actively in any social situation of their practice. Thus, reflexivity induces awareness of their roles and purpose in a situational context. Assessment and intervention in social work is in turn affected by reflexivity as their own assumptions influence practice situations.

Social Work Education

Social work has often been referred to as the human rights profession. It stands for social justice to all, and seeks to help the most marginalized and the underprivileged. Social Work education programs in India offer a range of specializations. Community development, family and child welfare, social welfare and correctional administration, human resource management, medical and psychiatric social work are the very common ones. Such information can be easily gleaned and confirmed by reviewing the curriculum of various schools of social work in India.

The social work program is also conducted in varying formats across institutions. It can be in the form of a separate bachelor's and master's program or an integrated five-year program, leading to a post graduate degree, with provision for lateral exits after the bachelor's degree. Likewise, field work also is carried out in different formats to suit the academic schedule and the place where the training program is being offered. It may be a concurrent field work program on pre-designated days, running parallel with routine classes. Consecutive two days, or select two separate days may be fixed in order to not disturb the theory classes. Students report to the concerned field agency/ community supervisor on the specified field work days, while the other days are devoted to classroom learning. It may also be a semester-end block placement field work program.

Kendall (1959) asserts that having a clear purpose and goal of field instruction will help social work educators to design the curriculum and also instruct them well. Although currently there are no disputes about field work being an integral part of social work education, she questions the ruminations that prevail about field work and highlights two basic concerns. They are: i) extent and type of skills; and ii) time to be spent on field work. She notes critics who argue that too much time is dedicated to field work, which otherwise could have been used in classroom learning. On the other hand, she also notes practitioners of social work voicing that field work time must be enhanced. The latter, in fact, have pointed out the huge gaps between "knowing" and "doing", owing to shortfalls of the field work component.

Thus, intense debates persist about turning around the curriculum in terms of being fair to classroom learning vis-a-vis field learning. In the midst of all these, different formats of field work practice prevail in different university programs. Kendall (1959) notes evidence about the advantages of a field work inclusive curriculum, as it caters to the emotional aspects of learning as well. What is disturbing according to her is a lack of uniformity and uniqueness of the practicum. Is it best left to the freedom of supervisors and

educational institutions? Or must we underscore the commonalities between classroom learning and field work learning? Will more precision and uniformity in the field work curriculum across geographies resolve some of these conflicts? Considering all these, she advocates working towards greater integration of the two components of class room and field; while simultaneously looking at all the methods of social work practice.

Field Work Methods

The various field work methods give ample scope to the social work student to hone his or her skills further while applying them in the variety of settings. Whether it is individual centred, or focussed on larger groups and communities, the range of services that social work can offer is very wide. Students can be engaged in research, administration, or even policy-making activities. Such a kind of engagement helps the trainees to prepare themselves well for the professional world. They not only get exposed to the problems that communities and agencies have to tackle with but also get accustomed to the routine functioning of agencies and the organisational climate. Likewise, placement in communities, whether rural or urban, exposes the trainees first hand to community dynamics.

It is beyond the scope of this paper to discuss the significance of all the methods here. However, an instance of the need for social welfare training in social work is cited here. Bernard Neugeboren (1971) had since emphasized that without inculcating the requisite knowledge and skill sets via such training, efficiency will be hampered. Moreover, social workers are no more only engaged in service delivery but administration as well. He also notes the shortcomings of formal social work administration training and emphasizes the requirement of such training to be on par with those in public administration and business administration. Planning, organizing, evaluating, analysing, controlling etc. are the skill sets he proposes for a social worker as essential. According to him, managing complex bureaucratic welfare organizations necessitate knowledge and skills to deal with, and comprehend the requirements of all the stakeholders, ranging from beneficiaries to staff as well as the sponsors. Such skills can be honed during field placements.

Additional Field Based Activities

Varieties of activities are incorporated into the curriculum to facilitate and promote field-based exposure and learning. Observation visits, rural camps, summer placements, educational tours, and block field placements, are the most commonly adopted formats in India. Within these activities, the trainee is encouraged to learn and further advance his/ her skills. Problem

identification and solving, listening, observation, interviewing, collating information, analysis, documentation, networking, co-operation, resource mobilization, advocacy etc. are some of the skills which the student learner is expected to demonstrate as an outcome of the field work process. A community exposure besides agency exposure also helps them to familiarize themselves with people from different backgrounds. Sensitivity about grassroots problems is thus inculcated. Therefore, exposing the trainees to the various dynamics of rural and urban settings via community placements in a multi-cultural country like India carries a lot of weight in the social work education program. The set of skills learned and sharpened may vary depending upon the placement setting, and of course upon other impinging factors like intrinsic motivation of the learner.

Planning the Field Work Process

Field work being integral to the social work curriculum, it is envisaged right at the beginning as an essential curriculum component. Agencies and communities with potential are identified right at the outset and liaised with. Experienced employees of the agencies, preferably with social work training, are sought as agency advisers. Where there are no social workers, a key person is identified as the adviser, who is in a suitably responsible position to mentor the students. The services of the trainees are solicited to assist and simultaneously learn from the agency. Depending upon the nature of the agency, a range of tasks may be assigned. However, the learning process must be kept paramount.

In the academic setting, faculty supervisors are assigned a set of students who will work and learn under such guidance. Besides an overall task plan at the outset, minute tasks are planned as per trainee inputs upon their return from the field visits. Achievement of task plans and overall student learning and progress is continually evaluated via field work reports after each visit. This not only keeps the trainees in sync with the work done in the field and the academic setting; but also endows a sense of responsibility and achievement. The regular necessity of reports ensures low absenteeism as well as enhances their analytical and reporting skills. 'Learning by doing' is heightened as they not only learn a range of activities in the field but are also encouraged to be reflexive and critical in their thinking. Such field learnings are internalised and they integrate with their classroom learnings.

It is pertinent to point out that an orientation program comprises the first step towards field work curriculum in any University program. Trainees are inducted by explaining the various merits and nuances of field work. They are also explained how various unforeseen hurdles may come along such as

lack of support from the agency supervisor, assignment of non-learning based “exploitative” tasks, and various other types of non-cooperation. Likewise, community dynamics can get volatile at different points in time. Or simply they may be inert and non-responsive to the social work trainees’ ideas and activities.

What is important is that field work is not an arbitrarily designed component of the curriculum. Fixed tasks which are to be systematically carried out under the supervision of both the agency guide and the faculty guide are specified well in advance. In community settings, key contact persons are identified and liaised with. Field work seminars with agency and community supervisors are conducted to enhance the mutual learning process. In social work, instruction and guidance from field instructors are of extreme importance. They help the students to not only learn theory and practice skill sets but also to internalise them. Attitudes, values, and ethics which can shape professional behaviour are learnt (Papouli, 2014).

Field work facilitates the understanding of social development issues. They can then be understood and tackled well by the trainees in their future professional lives. Human relationships, work environments, and various other skill-sets that are required in professional life can be developed during field work. Hager (2005) notes two ways of classifying learning theories. One views workplace-based learning as an outcome, and the other views it as a practice-based participatory process. Thus, the significance of field work is heightened in social work education.

Identifying Suitable Agencies

In most instances, social welfare and public service agencies, both governmental and non-governmental, are identified as it conforms to the kind of organisational settings that social work professionals would eventually be engaged with. However, this is certainly not a limiting factor. A range of other public sector and private sector organisations can also be liaised with. This is determined by the curriculum as well as the availability and response of such organisations. It is also to be noted that in industrialised places like Tamil Nadu, industrial establishments are also liaised with for student field placements. This is an outcome of student interest and the availability of these establishments. Specialisation courses like personnel management and industrial relations are offered in the education program to match these interests and geographical suitability. Contrarily, a less industrialised region like Northeast India would not be in a position to offer these kinds of establishments for field work placement. The choices will be confined to

government and non-government establishments. Such variations in geographies and their concomitant placement possibilities also impose themselves on the curriculum in intangible ways, and hence can affect the teaching learning process positively or negatively.

Kendall (1959) argues that the challenges of social work many times impose upon the academic program to make do with placement agencies which may not be equipped with the wherewithal to undertake student trainees. Hence, the teaching learning process gets affected. Staff shortages in welfare agencies are a common phenomenon and student services are often extracted to fulfil the agency's needs; such as running errands where no learning takes place. Student intake beyond the infrastructural capacity of the placement agency setting can also hamper the teaching learning process. The outcome, naturally, is a questionable quality of training and education. She therefore strongly advocates that deserving field placement agencies and field instructors must be given their share of glory by recognising them as partners of the academic programs. This could serve as motivators to the agencies.

Evaluation of Field Work

In Indian settings, as can be observed from a review of the social work education curriculum, individual counselling (IC) and group counselling (GC) are an essential and extremely significant component. A fixed number of students are assigned to a concerned faculty supervisor and the onus lies on the faculty to adopt the requisite mechanism to ensure that the students fully benefit from such counselling. During such counselling, discussions range from tentative work plan to be carried out in the field, resources mobilised, problems faced, and any other feedback from the agency/community supervisor. The reports submitted earlier are also discussed to ensure that there is continuous improvement in collating information, analysing and reporting them. Fieldwork diaries are maintained by the students and inspected by the faculty supervisor to ensure avoidance of absenteeism and proper conduct. Besides such evaluation of regular reports by the concerned faculty supervisor, there is also continuous feedback sought from the agency/ community supervisor via faculty visits to the setting, and other means of correspondence. This ensures an integrated as well as harmonious learning environment. At the end of each semester of learning, a viva voce is conducted, where an external examiner is invited to join the panel. They are thus continuously evaluated in this manner throughout the academic program. Recording, documentation, social mapping, resource mapping etc. are also learnt.

Anne E. Fortune, Mingun Lee and Alonzo Cavazos (2005) had conducted a study on 188 students from 4 social work programs to assess how motivation and field work performance are interrelated. According to them, students' intrinsic motivation and task value influenced their performance. They pointed out that field instructor evaluation did not influence motivation. This latter assumption is a limitation of the study. More studies on this account are warranted, where we can examine how extrinsic factors can also influence intrinsic motivation. However, their arguments have to be understood in a larger and suitable context, which is outside the scope of this paper.

It is likewise important to note that while students' personal zeal may be understood as intrinsic motivation, and the evaluators comments may be taken as extrinsic motivation, performance cannot be assessed via such a simple dichotomy. Varying degrees of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation will prevail up on an individual. Marylene Gagne and Edward L. (2005) talk about cognitive evaluation theory and self-determination theory as theories of work motivation. They cite Porter and Lawler (1968), who pointed out that intrinsic and extrinsic motivators go hand in hand. Negative feedback or negative evaluative outcome can demotivate self-driven learners and hamper their intrinsic motivation.

Making the Case for Field Based Learning

Papouli (2014), emphasizes the significance of field work education and how and why faculty as well as agency supervisors need to constantly monitor the learning process and provide requisite guidance. She looks at two learning approaches, namely; individual approaches and sociocultural learning approaches. She explains how sociocultural learning and field learning are interlinked, and thus emphasizes field work in social work education.

The global definition of social work profession further reiterates the significance of field work. It defines social work as a practiced-based profession, where theory and practice must go hand in hand; and both are equally significant. It combines classroom learning and field-based learning to enhance the overalls education experience. The social work profession seeks to promote social change, problem solving in human relationships, and the overall enhancement of human well-being. Theories of human behaviour and social systems play a pertinent role in its practice. The principles of human rights and social justice are fundamental to social work (International Federation of Social Workers, 2014).

Papouli (2014) highlights the lifelong impact of learning, where education is not merely for the sake of information but also transformation. Hence, there

is a need to focus on the learning process rather than solely on learning tasks. In social work education particularly, the student engages with field work and gradually forms his/ her professional identities. She also talks about how formal and informal learning types dominate social work literature; where the former is associated primarily with classroom-based learning, while the latter is associated with field situations and other experiential instances. However, both types of learning are affected by the socio-cultural, political, economic and historical space, within or around which such learning takes place. Hence, the 'person-in-environment' factor is very significant in the learning process. She further notes how Garrick (1998) points out that informal learning is influenced by one's social positioning, and can also in turn influence one's identity. Polanyi's (1976) distinction between explicit and implicit dimensions of learning is also noted. Such tacit or implicit knowledge also influence the learner in terms of values and attitudes. Experiential learning is thus accorded a high premium in social work education. Albert Bandura (1978) had also stressed upon how the person and the environment mutually influence one another (as cited in Papouli, 2014).

Since students get actively involved in field work, it opens new pathways for them to enhance their knowledge base. They interact with clients, peer groups, as well as other professionals. Noble (2001) adds that such field exposure helps initiate them early into professionalism and decision-making. Schneck (1995) even describes theory and practice as the two essential legs that must walk together. Lager and Robbins (2004) note that field work gives students the opportunity to evaluate interventions, develop cultural sensitivity, hone ethical values, and increases self-worth as a professional. Eraut (1994, 2000) underlines that practical knowledge and classroom-based learning together make up professional knowledge.

Factors Affecting Learning

Bogo observes that students' learnings are also affected by demography, keenness to learn, personal learning styles, and psychiatric disability as well. Being engaged in the learning process, proactiveness, and one's life experiences also influence learning. Fieldwork also exposes them to real-world problems and hence is advantageous (Bogo, 2010).

Sociocultural approaches to learning and the inherent situational learning, are also very vital to social work education. Learning via communities of practice, as expounded by Lave and Wenger (1991), necessitates involving the whole person and emphasizes the practice context. They advocate that the new learner observes the community of professionals and situates himself/herself within that culture of practice. The learners thus observe their peers,

instructors, and others around them in the situational environment. Behaviours, values and attitudes learnt here will also influence the new learner. Wenger (1999) further added that situational and experiential learning helps students to connect themselves well with their profession. He also believes that being a part of a community of practice influences us and our professionalism in many ways. Vygotsky (1978) spoke about proximate zones of development where he emphasizes the influence of social interactions in learning. Rogoff (1990) also refers to how learners enhance self-competence through guided participation.

Papouli (2014), however notes some very specific criticisms of the socio-cultural approaches to learning. She observes how Hay (1993) and Hager (2005) are doubtful of Lave and Wenger's view that learning is the outcome of participating with a community of experts. The power dynamics within an existing group would exert a different set of influence on the new learner. Guile and Griffiths (2001) also add that fully engaging with a community of practice must ensure learning opportunities endowed with room for a range of observations and discussions. This may not be the case everywhere.

Nonetheless, the entire process of learning to become a skilled social worker is a complex developmental journey. Different learners will have different learning needs and abilities; and hence present different outlooks towards learning. The strengths or weaknesses of learning theories apart, the truth remains that field work is integral to social work education; and learning does take place in many ways in the field. In order to facilitate this, the environment of learning must be given special attention. The faculty supervisor and agency supervisor must continuously monitor and evaluate the learning being exhibited by the students, and intervene wherever necessary. Steps must be taken to ensure that they are unduly not taken advantage of and exploited. A conducive environment induces the zeal to learn.

Cultural and Ethnic Diversity in Field Work

Field work must be designed keeping in mind the diversity of a place. Muriel Gladstein and Mildred Mailick (1986) talk about the need for meticulously planning the placement process, the agency context, and the agency/ community/ faculty advisor, keeping ethnic students' and the communities' needs in mind. Although not much literature is available on keeping ethnic students' needs in mind, they report that the Council on Social Work Education in 1968 constituted task forces to initiate minority contents to be incorporated in the curriculum. They note Kagwa's (1976) observation, which says that the objective was to gain familiarity with the history, culture,

and value systems of various ethnic groups and be sensitive to their unique needs and issues. Thus, efforts were always on to understand the ethnic minorities within the social work curriculum. However, they inform us that there is very scanty literature on ethnic students' needs as an important consideration for field work.

Gladstein and Mailick (1986) also discuss how issues like traveling, both in terms of time and costs, are important considerations. The placement setting also becomes an issue in terms of acceptance of the student social worker by the individual/ community belonging to another ethnic group, especially a majority group. Student placement preferences are difficult to estimate as they may not necessarily want to work among the same ethnic group, contrary to common notions. However, institutions do try to make efforts to suitably place them so that learning is enhanced.

Another aspect emphasized by Gladstein and Mailick (1986) is the culture of the agency, i.e., the placement setting. Expected behaviour in the agency setting may involve dress code, relationship with the staff, use of office space, communication patterns etc. They cite Hicks and Gullet (1975) to illustrate these observations and further add that such factors may either isolate the students or be supportive of them. The faculty advisor's unique position as a liaison between the institution, agency, student and field instructor is thus emphasized. An ethnic-sensitive approach must consider the strengths and weaknesses of these students and incorporate them while planning placements. They also underline Kagwa's (1976) opinion that the classroom faculty can facilitate by encouraging classroom discussions on ethnicity issues and their impact on class and field learning.

Summing Up

Kendall (1959) had noted that given the multiple factors that must be taken into consideration while incorporating field work as a curriculum component of social work education, a rationale versus rationalization dilemma for the pattern of field work continues. She notes how social work had its roots in agency-based training and was largely practice-oriented. University teaching and research were added to it later to give it a further edge as a profession. However, over time, field instruction as an essential component of the social work program was being continuously questioned by some. This is because it marks a departure from the curriculum of other professional courses. She adds that professionalism is expected of the student right from this point of contact with agencies/ communities via the field work process.

Such guided field practicum is one of the unique strengths of social work education. It creates opportunities for integrating theory with practice and pushes the student learners' motivations ahead. Contrarily, others are of the viewpoint that such a burden of professionalism in these early stages on the student are not feasible, as his/ her knowledge levels are at a very rudimentary stage and they may act on hunches instead. In such a scenario, she questions the rationale behind the student being expected to represent the agency. She further raises the question of whether a prolonged practice of such a pattern has rationalized the practice or does a strong rationale indeed exist. The varying range of opinions to this vexing question is noted by her (Kendall, 1959).

Therefore, to conclude, field work indeed remains an intrinsic character of social work education; keeping in mind the evolution of the discipline from its practice-based setting. There may be much jostling around for space to fit in varying formats of field work and to declare a typical format as a gamechanger. However, conventional wisdom will continue to prevail for a while and typologies of field work will have to be accommodated within the social work education program. So long as societies and cultures are dynamic and continue to be in motion, field work perhaps cannot take a static uniform stand. This is the uniqueness of the practice.

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